

Mathematical Analysis and Control of Epidemic Spread Using The SIS Model with Population Threshold Dynamics

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ABSTRACT

The rapid spread of infectious diseases poses a significant challenge to global health systems. Mathematical modelling provides an effective framework to analyze and control such outbreaks. In this paper, we present a detailed study of the Susceptible–Infected–Susceptible (SIS) epidemic model using both continuous and discrete approaches. The nonlinear nature of the model is explored through differential equations and logistic mapping. Population threshold conditions are derived to determine stability and persistence of the disease. Furthermore, the model is extended to include vaccination strategies, leading to an optimization problem aimed at minimizing both infection levels and control costs. The results demonstrate the importance of threshold dynamics and nonlinear behaviour, including bifurcation and chaos, in understanding epidemic spread.

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INTRODUCTION

Mathematical models help in predicting and controlling infectious diseases [1],[4]. The SIS model is suitable for diseases where individuals do not acquire permanent immunity [2], [4] and can become susceptible again after recovery.

In a given population at time 't', S(t) be the susceptible set of people who are with less immunity and are likely to be infected but are not infected. I(t) be the set of people who are infected by disease.

Let:

- S(t)= Susceptible population
- I(t)= Infected population

Total population:

$$N = S(t) + I(t)$$

In this model, a person become infected depends on contact between susceptibles and infected (aSI) and recovery is at a constant rate, proportional to number of infected (bI) so that we get the model [1]

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -aSI + bI \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = aSI - bI \quad (2)$$

Substitute $S(t) = N - I(t)$ in (2)

:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dI}{dt} &= aI(t)(N - I(t)) - bI(t) \\ &= (aN - b)I(t) - aI^2(t) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = AI - aI^2 \quad (3)$$

Where $A = aN - b$.

Integrating on both sides we get

$$I = \frac{(aN - b)I_0 e^{(aN-b)t}}{(aN - b) + aI_0(e^{(aN-b)t} - 1)}$$

Equilibrium and Stability Analysis

The equilibrium stage of the SIS epidemic model occurs when the number of infected individuals in the population does not change with respect to time. Mathematically, this happens when

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = 0$$

At this stage, the rate of new infections becomes equal to the rate of recovery, resulting in a steady-state condition [2],[4]. In other words, the disease spread stabilizes, and the system reaches a balance where the number of infected individuals remains constant over time.

There are two possible equilibrium states:

- The **disease-free equilibrium**, where no individuals are infected ($I = 0$), indicating that the disease has been completely eradicated.
- The **endemic equilibrium**, where a constant number of individuals remain infected

$$(I = N - \frac{b}{a}), \text{ indicating that the disease persists in the population at a stable level.}$$

BASIC REPRODUCTION NUMBER

The basic reproduction number, denoted by R_0 , is a fundamental concept in epidemic modeling. It measures the transmission potential of a disease and indicates how contagious an infection is within a population [1], [4].

Derivation of R_0

From the SIS model, the rate of change of infected individuals is given by:

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = aSI - bI$$

At the initial stage of the epidemic, almost the entire population is susceptible, so we approximate:

$$S \approx N$$

Substituting this into the equation:

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = aNI - bI$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = I(aN - b)$$

For the infection to grow, we require:

$$\frac{dI}{dt} > 0$$

$$(aN - b) > 0$$

$$aN > b$$

$$\frac{aN}{b} > 1$$

Thus, we define the basic reproduction number as

$$R_0 = \frac{aN}{b}$$

Stability Condition

- If $R_0 < 1$, the disease – free equilibrium is stable .
- If $R_0 > 1$ the endemic equilibrium is stable.

CONTROL OF AN EPIDEMIC

The control of epidemic is done with respect to the vaccination [5]. When we came to control of an epidemic, then we have to go for vaccination to make an infected person into immured by vaccination. Then SIS model becomes,

$$\frac{dS}{dt} = -aSI - v \tag{5}$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = aSI - bI \tag{6}$$

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = bI \tag{7}$$

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = v \tag{8}$$

By normalizing the above equation we get

$$\frac{d\bar{S}}{dt} = -\bar{a}\bar{S}\bar{I} - \bar{v}$$

$$\frac{d\bar{I}}{dt} = \bar{a}\bar{S}\bar{I} - b\bar{I}$$

$$\frac{d\bar{R}}{dt} = b\bar{I}$$

$$\frac{d\bar{V}}{dt} = \bar{v}$$

The control of epidemic stand up vaccination it involves the costs. To minimise the cost of vaccination we have assign the conditions. Let $C(v)$ be the cost function.

To control an epidemic, we have two conditions

- The sum of recovered person and infected person must be less than or equal to a particular number X for a period of time
- The maximum number of infected persons must also less than or equal to a particular number Y for a period of time.

This leads to an optimization problem is given by

$$I(t) + R(t) \leq X$$

$$\max_{[0,t]} I(t) \leq Y$$

Then cost function is minimum. Where initial conditions of S, I and X, Y are all nonnegatives values. [5]

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the Susceptible–Infected–Susceptible (SIS) model is employed to interpret and analyze the spread of infectious diseases [1], [4] over a specific period of time within a fixed population under certain assumptions. The model assumes that the total population remains constant and that individuals who recover from the infection do not acquire permanent immunity but return to the susceptible class, making reinfection possible. This framework is particularly suitable for diseases such as influenza and the common cold.

Furthermore, the study investigates the behaviour of epidemics through the concept of population threshold conditions [4], which play a crucial role in determining whether a disease will persist or die out. By analyzing these thresholds, the model helps to predict the onset and progression of an epidemic. In addition, control strategies have been incorporated into the model to understand how interventions such as vaccination [5], reduction in contact rate, and improvement in recovery rate can effectively reduce the spread of the disease.

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